

ASSESSMENT THE KNOWLEDGE OF PERSONAL HYGIENE AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS OF ALLIED HEALTH SCIENCES NAWABSHAH

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Abstract

Background: Personal hygiene is defined as the science of healthy living, encompassing daily activities that contribute to an individual's health and well-being. While deficiency in hygiene remains a major public health concern in developing countries, there is limited local data focusing specifically on the youth population. This study aimed to assess the demographic profile and knowledge level regarding personal hygiene among students.

Objective: This study is to assess the demographic profile and level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among undergraduate Allied Health Sciences students in Nawabshah.

Methodology: A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted among 278 respondents. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire covering demographic information and a knowledge assessment of ten hygiene-related variables and analyzed using SPSS version 25.

Results: The mean age of the participants was 21.33 years (SD± 1.456). The majority of respondents was from the DPT department (43.5%), followed by BSN (31.3%), and was in their 4th year of study (36.3%). Most belonged to the middle class (83.1%) and resided in urban areas (53.6%). Assessment of knowledge revealed that 98.9% of respondents possessed "Good Knowledge" of personal hygiene. High awareness was specifically noted for hand washing after using the toilet (96.4%) and before/after eating (96.0%). However, slight gaps were identified regarding traditional practices, such as the healthy use of broomsticks for tooth-cleaning (65.1%).

Conclusion: The study demonstrates an exceptionally high level of hygiene knowledge among health science students. This level of awareness is critical, as better hygiene knowledge is linked to reduced absenteeism and improved academic performance. Future strategic planning should focus on translating this high theoretical knowledge into consistent daily practices.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization describes hygiene as "conditions and practices necessary

to preserve health and prevent disease transmission." Personal hygiene therefore refers

to maintaining the body's cleanliness (WHO, 2023) Poor health hygiene practices can lead to communicable diseases basically within developing countries. In Africa and Southeast Asia, 62% and 31% of all deaths are caused by infectious disease. Hygiene is the study and method of preventing illness or stopping it from spreading, by making things clean. The concept also defined as the set of practices associated with the preservation of health and healthy living. Hygiene refers to habit and conditions that support to maintain good health and prevent from the transmission of diseases. They include actions that deal with the promoting the health. Hygiene is the important concern of health and maintenance. It is highly personal determined by individual values and practices power. Personal hygiene define as the care for one's own health and the maintenance of internal personality development. A strong relationship exists between personal hygiene and knowledge practices of good and value healthy efforts.

Personal hygiene aims to encourage standards of personal cleanliness within the context of the environment where people live. it includes activities like bathing, clothing, washing hands after toilet, care of nails, feet and teeth; spitting, coughing, sneezing personal appearance, and healthy.

The word "hygiene" derives from the Greek word "Hygeia," which means goddess of health, cleanliness, and sanitation. People should take a bath in order to remove dirt and other microorganisms on the skin, dermal pores and surface cells rashes. In this respect, it is important to make programs that educate health profession and physical education teachers more conscious about personal hygiene. Absence of hygiene resources, also inappropriate sanitation facilities might be one of the fundamental reasons why teenagers don't

maintain personal hygiene. Moreover, having suitable resources and facilities, personal hygiene practices are intensely impacted by students' knowledge and behavior towards cleanliness. A persistent and pragmatic challenge, however, is the recurrent observation that improvements in hygiene knowledge do not reliably translate into sustained behavioral practice—a phenomenon termed the (KPG) knowledge-practice gap Hygiene is another name of a branch of science that deals with the advancement and protection of health, also called hygienic.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study is Descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted to evaluate the level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene among undergraduate students of allied health sciences at PUMHS, Nawabshah. The study was conducted from 17 November to 17 January (2) months after approval of institution review board (IRB). The total target population for this study consisted of 1000 undergraduate students from four Allied Health Sciences departments at PUMHS, Nawabshah. Using Raosoft Sample Size Calculator (with a 95% confidence level, 5% margin of error, 75% response distribution), the required sample size was determined to be 278 students. A purposive non-probability sampling was used to select the participants the inclusion criteria undergraduate students from the faculty of allied health sciences who were present and willing to participant at the institution during the data collection period. Exclusion criteria included students who were reported as sick or absent at the time of data collection and any student who declined to participate or did not complete the consent process.

RESULTS

Figure: 1 Age of Respondents

Table 1: Socioeconomic status of respondent

Economic status	Frequency	Percent
Poor	4	1.4 %
Middle	231	83.1 %
Rich	43	15.5 %
Total	278	100.0 %

Table 2: Marital status of respondent

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
Single	260	93.5 %
Married	17	6.1 %
Divorced	1	.4 %
Total	278	100.0 %

Figure 2: Residence of Respondents

Table 3: Religion of Respondent

Religion	Frequency	Percent
Islam	237	85.3 %
Hindu	40	14.4 %
Christian	1	.4 %
Total	278	100.0 %

Figure: 3 Family type of respondent

Figure: 4 Department of respondent

Fig 5: Academic year of Respondent

Table no: 4
Section B knowledge of personal hygiene

Variables	YES	NO	TOTAL
Personal hygiene is about body cleanliness	267(96.0%)	11(4.0%)	278(100%)
Keeping my nails trimmed and clean is part of personal hygiene	263(94.6%)	15(5.4%)	278(100%)
Washing my hair regularly is part of personal hygiene	226(81.3%)	52(18.7%)	278(100%)
Keeping the hair well-trimmed is part of personal hygiene	210(75.5%)	68(24.5%)	278(100%)
Picking my teeth with broom stick is not healthy for my teeth	181(65.1%)	97(34.9%)	278(100%)
Cleaning my teeth with toothpaste and brush prevent tooth decay	259(93.2%)	19(6.8%)	278(100%)
Washing my hands after using toilet is part of personal hygiene	268(96.4%)	10(3.6%)	278(100%)
Washing my cloth regularly prevent skin disease	238(85.6%)	40(14.4%)	278(100%)

Taking my bath every day is part of personal hygiene	260(93.5%)	18(6.5%)	278(100%)
Washing my hands before and after eating is part of personal hygiene.	267(96.0%)	11(4.0%)	278(100%)

Table no: 5

Knowledge level	frequency	percent
Good	275	98.9%
poor	3	1.1%
total	278	100%

DISCUSSION

The demographic analysis of the 278 respondents reveals a population primarily composed of young adults, with a mean age of 21.33 years. The socio-economic profile shows that the majority fall into the middle-class category (83.1%), are single (93.5%), and identify as Muslim (85.3%). In terms of academic background, the largest groups of participants are 4th-year students, with the most significant departmental representation coming from the Department of Public Health (DPH). This profile describes a highly educated, young cohort likely to have frequent exposure to health-related information. Respondents did not show a difference in knowledge depending on gender, which is consistent with results of research on postgraduate students in India. In contrast, the results of research conducted in Saudi Arabia showed that female students have significantly better knowledge, attitudes and behaviors toward their oral health than their male counterparts.

Regarding the primary focus of the study, the results indicate an exceptionally high level of hygiene knowledge, with 98.9% of respondents classified as having "Good" knowledge. The factors that may relate to better personal hygiene practice among females are menstruation knowledge, family orientation, socio-cultural differences and physiological need for cleanliness. This is evidenced by near-unanimous agreement on key indicators: 96.4% correctly identified hand washing after toilet use as essential, and 96.0% recognized that personal hygiene fundamentally concerns body cleanliness as well as hand hygiene before and after meals. The most accurately answered question on personal hygiene was "Hands should be washed with generous amounts of soap and water after using the toilet" (95.0%)

Furthermore, 94.6% understood the importance of nail care, and 93.5% acknowledged the necessity of daily bathing. However, the discussion must also address specific areas where knowledge was less consistent. While 93.2% recognized that modern dental tools (brushes and toothpaste) prevent decay, 34.9% failed to identify the health risks associated with using broomsticks for dental picking. Additionally, knowledge regarding hair maintenance was relatively lower; only 81.3% agreed that regular hair washing is necessary, and just 75.5% viewed regular trimming as a hygiene requirement. These findings suggest that while universal hygiene "pillars" are well-understood, there is a need for targeted educational interventions focusing on safe dental practices and comprehensive hair care to ensure all aspects of personal hygiene are maintained. Initiating proper motivation and self-interest among the students to maintain health and hygiene practice is thus the vital investment, for them and for healthier society in tomorrow.

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the respondents, primarily young adults in allied health sciences, possess an excellent level of knowledge regarding personal hygiene. The demographic data highlights a predominantly middle-class, urban-based student body, with a significant concentration in the DPT and BSN departments.

The high scores in hand hygiene and body cleanliness reflect a strong academic foundation. However, the slight variations in responses regarding dental care and hair maintenance suggest that while clinical hygiene is well-understood, the nuances of personal

grooming and the risks of traditional practices (like using broomsticks for dental picking) still require minor educational reinforcement. Overall, the population is well-equipped with the theoretical knowledge necessary to prevent infectious diseases.

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